

TECHNISCHE
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WIEN

Data management plan (DMP)

WordStream: Interactive Visualization for Topic Evolution

Version	Effective date	Description of document/changes
1.0	05/12/2024	First version of the DMP – created for the start of the project

Level of distribution		This DMP is licensed under a Creative Commons Attribution 4.0 International License (CC BY 4.0) . It is publicly available under https://handle.test.datacite.org/10.70124/3fjcd-5xc41 .
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Project details

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List of acronyms

DMP	data management plan
RDM	research data management
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Introduction

Science Europe practical guide, FAIR data

A DMP is a structured document that keeps record of what research data is created and what happens to that data during and after a project. It helps with planning the research process and defining responsibilities in a research project involving several researchers or institutions.

For writing this DMP, we followed [the recommendations of Science Europe](#) as they reflect the guidelines agreed upon by the major funders in Europe.

To make our data FAIR, they generally will be treated according to the following criteria:

- We will make our data findable, by uploading it to a data repository that provides a persistent identifier, and adding relevant metadata.
- We will make our data accessible by providing open access to data, wherever possible. In cases, where open access is not possible, we will provide meaningful metadata plus contact information for access requests.
- We will make our data interoperable by providing and describing data in a way that is common within our domain by using the same file formats, schemas and vocabularies. We will provide good documentation for all our datasets.
- We will make our data reusable by adding metadata and comprehensive Readme files to all published datasets. The descriptions include details on the methodology used, analytical and procedural information. In case of publication, licenses for code and data will always be assigned and clearly marked.

Relevant Policies and Guidelines

- TU Wien Policy for Research Data Management: <https://www.tuwien.at/index.php?eID=dms&s=4&path=Directives%20and%20Regulations%20of%20the%20Rectorate/Policy%20for%20Research%20Data%20Management.pdf>
- TU Wien Code of Conduct – Rules to Ensure Good Scientific Practice: <https://www.tuwien.at/index.php?eID=dms&s=4&path=Directives%20and%20Regulations%20of%20the%20Rectorate/Code%20of%20Conduct%20E2%80%93%20Rules%20to%20Ensure%20Good%20Scientific%20Practice.pdf>
- Directives and Regulations of the TU Wien Rectorate: <https://www.tuwien.at/en/tu-wien/organisation/central-divisions/data-protection-and-document-management/directives-regulations/>
- TU Wien Data Protection: <https://www.tuwien.at/en/tu-wien/organisation/central-divisions/data-protection-and-document-management/data-protection-at-tu-wien>
- Other (e.g. from a project partner)

1. Data description

1a Lists of datasets that will be reused or produced

Produced datasets

dataset ID	title	type	format	estimated volume	contains sensitive data

Reused datasets

dataset ID	title	PID (e.g. DOI) or source	rights (e.g. license)	contains sensitive data
R1	DER STANDARD - Articles from 2023	https://handle.test.datacite.org/10.70124/3fjcd-5xc41		no

1b Data generation and reuse

Methods and software used for data generation and reuse

This dataset will be used to visualize the topic evolution in Austria throughout the year. By analyzing the text data, the aim is to track how key topics and themes emerged, developed, and declined over time. Using the WordStream visualization approach, the analysis will highlight the most relevant terms and their dynamics, providing insights into public discourse, news priorities, and societal trends in Austria in 2023. This will enable an intuitive exploration of the year's key events. The project will employ Python for data processing and the visualization will be created using D3.js.

2. Documentation and data quality

2a Data organisation, metadata and documentation

The TU Wien repository supports data versioning by automatically tracking and storing different versions of datasets whenever updates are made. Each version includes version numbers, modification dates. Unique identifiers (e.g., DOIs) are assigned to datasets, allowing precise referencing of specific versions. Researchers can access and retrieve all versions, preserving the integrity of original data and supporting reproducibility.

The metadata for the dataset can be found in its description within the repository. This includes detailed explanations of the column names, which define their meaning and format, providing clarity about the structure and content of the data. Additionally, the dataset's description contains other relevant metadata, such as the purpose of the dataset and methods of data collection. This will help others to identify, discover and reuse our data.

2b Data quality control

The following data quality checks will be done: peer review of data.

3. Storage and backup during research process

3a Storage and backup facilities

For the duration of the project, storage and backup of data will be ensured by the project manager in cooperation with the responsible representative of TU.it. The infrastructure of TU Wien will be used for this purpose.

R1 (DER STANDARD - Articles from 2023) will be stored on TUfiles: TUfiles is a central and readily available network drive with daily backups and regular snapshots provided by TU.it. It is suitable for storing data with moderate access requirements, but high availability demands that allows full control of allocating authorisations. Only authorized staff members will have access.

3b Data security and protection of sensitive data

We pay strict attention to compliance with the relevant institutional and national data protection policies listed in the introduction of this document. At this stage, it is not foreseen to process any sensitive data in the project. If this changes, advice will be sought from the data protection specialist at TU Wien, and the DMP will be updated.

Access to data during research:

dataset ID	selected project members	all other project members	the public
R1	writing	writing	no access

4. Legal and ethical requirements

4a Personal data

At this stage, it is not foreseen to process any personal data in the project. If this changes, advice will be sought from the data protection specialist at TU Wien, and the DMP will be updated.

4b Intellectual property rights and ownership

Legal restrictions on how data is processed and shared are specified in the Terms and Conditions of DER STANDARD. The restrictions relate to datasets R1 (DER STANDARD - Articles from 2023). The legal restrictions are based on the following: Further use and reproduction beyond personal use is not permitted.

4c Ethical issues

No particular ethical issue is foreseen with the data to be used or produced by the project. This section will be updated if issues arise.

5. Data sharing and long-term preservation

5a Data publication and access conditions

As far as possible, obtained datasets will be published in repositories. Details on access conditions, reuse licenses, reasons for restrictions, etc. are collected in the table below.

dataset ID	access conditions	restrictions / embargo reasons	estimated publication date	location for publication (repository)	PID	license
R1	Open	Access to the data is restricted to ensure controlled usage and to verify whether the data is being utilized beyond personal use. This restriction allows for proper oversight of data usage, ensuring that it aligns with the intended purposes and complies with and legal requirements.	03/12/2024	TU Wien Research Data		CC BY-NC 4.0

Methods or software needed to access and use data: To reuse the data, all that is needed is software capable of reading CSV files, such as Excel, Python, R, or any similar tool.

5b Long-term preservation and deletion of data

dataset ID	location for long-term storage	minimum retention period (≥ 10 years)	foreseeable research uses and/or users
R1	TU Wien Research Data	10 years	Members of the scientific community

6. RDM responsibilities and resources

6a RDM-roles and responsibilities

The contact person will direct the data management process overall, with the research assistants responsible for ensuring metadata production, day-to-day cross-checks, back-up and other quality control activities are maintained.

6b Resources

There are no costs dedicated to data management and ensuring that data will be FAIR.

Cost name	Cost type	Description	Unit	Value
Estimated total costs				0